

Application of *p*-Dimethylaminoanil of 2-Thiopheneglyoxal in Gravimetric Estimation of Ruthenium(III), Rhodium(III), Iridium(III) and Platinum(IV)

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p-Dimethylaminoanil of 2-thiopheneglyoxal, which precipitates several platinum metal ions in alkaline medium at different pH, has been used as gravimetric reagent in the estimation of Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Ir^{III} and Pt^{IV} cations individually.

ALTHOUGH, ketoanils are well known for their coordination properties, and industrial and medicinal uses, analytical applications of these compounds in chromatographic¹⁻³ and gravimetric⁴⁻⁶ estimations of metal ions have also been reported. The use of *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 2-thiopheneglyoxal (DMATG) in gravimetric estimation of Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Ir^{III} and Pt^{IV}, which has been unknown hitherto, is reported in this communication, in continuation to our previous work⁴⁻⁶.

Experimental

DMATG was synthesised⁷ by using reagent grade (B.D.H.) chemicals. Platinum metal chlorides (John Metthy) were used as supplied. Stock solution of DMATG prepared by dissolving its known quantity was used as such whereas solutions of metal salts were standardised⁸ before use. Solvent of all solutions was acetone—water (9 : 1, w/v).

pH measurements were done with a Phillips pH meter by using saturated calomel and glass electrodes. pH of the solutions was adjusted by sodium

hydroxide solution. Precipitates were filtered out with G₄ sintered glass crucibles.

Elemental analysis of complexes was done micro-analytically at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

Procedure: A dilute (0.1%, w/v) solution of DMATG was added slowly with constant stirring till in excess to the metal chloride solution, and pH (Table 1) was adjusted so as to observe quantitative precipitation with dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. Precipitate was allowed to settle and filtered. Precipitated complex, which was washed with water, ether and chloroform successively, was dried at 100° and weighed.

Results and Discussion

Compositions of complexes (Table 1) have been deduced from Fenger's method⁹ and confirmed by elemental analysis done after heating the precipitates at 100°. Useful range for each metal, relative error and tolerance of foreign ions are stated in Table 2.

TABLE 1—COLOUR, ANALYSIS AND PRECIPITATION pH OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	pH for quantitative precipitation	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)	
			Metal	N
Ru(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS) ₂ (OH) ₂	9.7±0.1	Gray	14.9 (15.2)	8.5 (8.3)
Rh(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS) ₂ (OH) ₂	8.2±0.2	Gray orange	15.0 (15.2)	8.2 (8.4)
Ir(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS) ₂ (OH) ₂	10.3±0.1	Dirty yellow	24.8 (25.3)	6.9 (7.3)
Pt(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS) ₂ (OH) ₄	9.6±0.1	Brown	24.9 (25.0)	7.0 (7.2)

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION

Metal	Useful range mg	Relative error %	Tolerance of foreign ions (mg)
Ru ^{III}	8-147	±0.34	Pd ^{II} (25), Os ^{IV} (20), Ir ^{III} (0.5), Au ^{III} (5), Hg ^{II} (8), borate (55), chloride (40), bromide (45), iodide (60), sulphate (25), acetate (35)
Rh ^{III}	8-182	±0.35	Ru ^{III} (0.4), Pd ^{II} (35), Os ^{IV} (35), Ir ^{III} (0.4), Pt ^{IV} (0.3), Au ^{III} (8), Hg ^{II} (8), chloride (45), borate (55), bromide (65), sulphate (40), iodide (80), acetate (55)
Ir ^{III}	8-102	±0.30	Pd ^{II} (15), Os ^{IV} (12), Au ^{III} (4), chloride (40), bromide (40), acetate (40), sulphate (20), borate (25)
Pt ^{IV}	6-91	±0.31	Pd ^{II} (20), Os ^{IV} (15), Ir ^{III} (0.5), Au ^{III} (8), Hg ^{II} (8), borate (40), chloride (45), bromide (35), iodide (35), sulphate (30)

Since metal ions precipitate quantitatively in alkaline medium, their separation in mixture(s) was not possible. Low conversion factors reveal high sensitivity of this method.

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